

THE ROLE OF INNOVATION IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF CEO'S CHARACTERISTICS ON PERFORMANCE OF TECHNOLOGY FIRMS IN VIET NAM

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

A firm's progress frequently hinges on its chief executive officer's (CEO's) decisions. Extensive research has consistently indicated a correlation between CEO's characteristics and the firm's innovation and performance. From the management perspective, a CEO's characteristics significantly influence the decision-making process and the firm's overall performance.

This study investigates how firm innovation mediates the relationship between various CEO characteristics such as age, tenure, gender, educational background, founder status, duality status and overconfidence with performance of technology firms in Vietnam. Previous research has argued the relationship between CEO characteristics, firm innovation, and firm performance. This study has proposed a conceptual model and nine hypotheses, which will be tested to investigate how firm innovation can mediate the relationship between CEO characteristics such as age, gender, tenure, educational background, founder status, duality status, overconfidence, and firm performance in technology firms in Vietnam.

Hence, the present research study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How does CEO characteristics such as CEO age, gender, educational background, founder status, tenure, duality status and overconfidence affect the firm innovation of technology firms in Vietnam?
2. How does firm innovation influence firm performance of technology firms in Vietnam?
3. To what extent does firm innovation mediate the relationship between CEO characteristics such as CEO age, gender, educational background, founder status,

tenure, duality, overconfidence, and firm performance in technology firms in Vietnam?

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

For a long time, researchers have debated about three research relationships: The first is the relationship between firm performance and firm innovation (Ar, 2012; Atalay et al., 2013; OECD/Eurostat, 2018; Ramadani et al., 2019; Rousseau et al., 2016). The second is about the influence of the characteristics of CEO on firm innovation (Barker & Mueller, 2002; Cai et al., 2018; Cho & Kim, 2017; Galasso & Simcoe, 2011; Kitchell, 1997; Le Blanc et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2020; Li & Yang, 2019; Wang et al., 2022). The third is to learn about the influence of the characteristics of CEO on firm performance (Abebe & Alvarado, 2013; Gottesman & Morey, 2010; Green & Homroy, 2018; Jayaraman et al., 2000b; Khan & Vieito, 2013a; King et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2018; Prasad & Junni, 2017; Rahman & Chen, 2022; Salehi & Moghadam, 2019; Shen & Cannella, 2002; Wang et al., 2016).

The main objective of the research is to study how the firm innovation mediates the influence effect of CEO's characteristics such as CEO's age, gender, tenure, educational qualification, educational background (i.e., field of study and educational qualification), founder status, duality and CEO overconfidence on firm performance. Based on the literature review, research questions and research objectives, the conceptual model for the influence of CEO characteristics on firm innovation and firm performance for technology firms within the context of Vietnam is proposed.

The conceptual model illustrates the relationship between CEO's characteristics to firm innovation and how innovation can mediate the relationship between CEO's characteristics and firm performance.

This study will research the relationship between CEO characteristics with firm innovation and firm performance and how firm innovation can mediate the relationship between CEO characteristics and firm performance. The nine hypotheses will be summarized as follows: please rephrase the hypotheses below.

H1: CEO age will negatively affect firm innovation in technology firms.

H2: Female CEOs will outperform male CEOs on firm innovation in technology firms.

H3: CEO tenure will positively affect firm innovation in technology firms.

H4a: CEOs with IT and engineering educational backgrounds will outperform CEOs with non-IT and non-engineering educational backgrounds on firm innovation in technology firms.

H4b: CEOs with higher degree educational qualification will positively affect firm innovation compared to those with lower degree and no qualification in technology firms.

H5: Founder CEO will perform better than non-founder CEO on firm innovation in technology firms.

H6: CEOs who do not concurrently serve as Chairman/Chairwoman will positively affect firm innovation than CEOs who hold both roles in technology firms.

H7: CEO overconfidence will positively affect firm innovation in technology firms.

H8: Firm innovation will positively affect firm performance in technology firms.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This research aims to explore the relationship between CEO characteristics and firm performance and firm innovation. Hence, the quantitative research technique is deemed suitable for this type of study. The concept of quantitative design in research pertains to a systematic methodology that emphasizes the collection and analysis of numerical data. This approach quantitatively measures behaviours, views, attitudes, and other specified characteristics to draw generalizable conclusions from a broader population sample. Quantitative research designs encompass descriptive, correlational, causal-comparative/quasi-experimental, and experimental approaches (Cohen et al., 2018; Creswell, 2018).

Firstly, a literature review is the most fundamental step in exploring previous research on the relationship between CEO characteristics, firm performance, and firm innovation. Indeed, upper-echelon theory has indicated that CEO characteristics, including demographic and psychological characteristics, influence the CEO's decision-making behavior, indirectly affecting firm performance and innovation. The literature review reveals that, from past to present, there have been no specific studies on the relationship between six demographic characteristics, including: "age", "gender", "educational background", "CEO founder status", "tenure", "CEO duality" and one psychological characteristic, "CEO overconfidence" with both firm innovation and firm performance. Additionally, the subjects of this study are technology firms in Vietnam. Based on these theoretical and practical problems that need to be studied, a conceptual model has been developed with nine hypotheses.

The second step is to collect data to test the conceptual model and hypotheses. However, due to the characteristics of the Vietnamese economy, technology firms are typically divided into two main groups. The first group comprises firms with

ample revenues and significant influence listed on the Hanoi Stock Exchange (HNX) and the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange (HSX). The technology-influenced firms listed on the stock exchange include over 30 firms. Data for this group is usually collected from the HNX and HSX web portals. The first group includes publicly traded companies with publicly available data, as Vietnamese law requires, but the number of technology firms is limited (less than 100). The second group comprises technology firms of various sizes, from small to large, that have not yet been listed on the stock exchange. According to statistics from the Ministry of Information and Communications of Vietnam, there are currently about 70,000 firms operating in the technology sector in Vietnam (Ministry of Information and Communication, 2023) . However, these firms are not listed on the stock exchange; consequently, statistical data regarding these firms is not publicly available for access and research. Therefore, for the second group, the research method will be survey research. Given the characteristics of the Vietnamese economy in the technology sector, this study will use survey research as the primary research method.

Designing the questionnaire questions for researching technology firms in Vietnam is based on the measure scales of each variable under study. The language used to construct the questionnaire is English, as the referenced materials regarding CEO characteristics, firm performance, and firm innovation all utilize English, the international language. However, English is not the native language in Vietnam, and its use may pose difficulties for respondents. Consequently, the questionnaire will have a Vietnamese version directly translated from the English version by a translator who has English professional qualification and graduated from University of Languages. Then, this Vietnamese version will be back translated (Brislin, 1970) into English by another translator who also has English professional qualification and graduated from University of Languages. This is followed by comparing the original and back-translated versions to ensure that the information remains unchanged and to adjust if necessary.

The pilot survey is regarded as a preliminary step to test the validity of the research tool, including the questionnaire (Creswell, 2018). The purpose of the pilot survey is to ensure that the questionnaire is suitable and effective for formal research. Creswell also suggests that the use of a pilot survey allows for the identification of potential factors that could affect the accuracy and reliability of the research, such as ambiguity in survey questions or difficulties in the data collection process (Creswell, 2018).

Conducting a pilot survey for research on Vietnamese technology firms is important. Since the measurement variables are constructed based on literature sourced primarily from studies conducted in Western countries. Therefore, the pilot survey is used to adjust the questionnaire to fit the conditions in Vietnam. An essential aspect of the pilot survey is the necessary sample size. According to

Johanson and Brook (2010), there are various sampling standards for pilot tests in social sciences, but the sample size is typically between 10 and 30 (Johanson & Brooks, 2010). Isaac and Michael (1995) explain that a sample size of 10 to 30 offers numerous advantages in analysis and calculation and can effectively test hypotheses (Isaac & Michael, 1995). Similarly, Hill (1998) suggests that a necessary sample size for a pilot test ranging from 10 to 30 increases the reliability of the research (Hill, 1998).

From previous research proposals, the suggested sample size for a pilot survey is 30 (Hill, 1998; Isaac & Michael, 1995; Johanson & Brooks, 2010). Additionally, it is anticipated that a portion of the draft surveys collected during the pilot survey may not yield valid responses. Assuming that the rate of valid surveys will be around 60% - 70%, therefore it is necessary to send out approximately 50 draft surveys. These drafts will be sent to the Hanoi Young Business Association by email, targeting CEOs of manufacturing and technology firms in Hanoi, Vietnam. The collected survey samples will be carefully analysed to adjust the content of the questionnaire, and CEOs who responded in the pilot test will not be included in the main survey to ensure the reliability of the research.

Ultimately, the final questionnaire will be distributed to CEOs of technology firms in Vietnam via a web-based survey. As indicated in the questionnaire, all information provided by the survey participants will be kept strictly confidential. The collected data will be used solely for the purpose of this research and will not be utilized for any other commercial purposes. Both the English and Vietnamese versions of the questionnaire are included in the Appendices section.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we initially explore the definitions of firm performance, firm innovation, and CEO characteristics, which include CEO age, CEO gender, CEO educational background, CEO tenure, CEO founder status, CEO duality, and CEO overconfidence. Thus, previous research has demonstrated a relationship between CEO characteristics and firm performance (Abebe & Alvarado, 2013; Gottesman & Morey, 2010; Green & Homroy, 2018; Jayaraman et al., 2000b; Khan & Vieito, 2013; King et al., 2016; D. Liu et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2018; Prasad & Junni, 2017; Rahman & Chen, 2022; Salehi & Moghadam, 2019; Shen & Cannella, 2002; G. Wang et al., 2016) as well as firm innovation (Barker & Mueller, 2002; Cai et al., 2018; S. Y. Cho & Kim, 2017; Galasso & Simcoe, 2011; Kitchell, 1997; Le Blanc et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2020; M. Li & Yang, 2019; Q. Wang et al., 2022). Therefore, the problem statement of this research aims to investigate further the impact of CEO characteristics on firm innovation and firm performance of technology firms in Vietnam context.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abebe, M., & Alvarado, D. (2013). Founder-CEO status and firm performance: an exploratory study of alternative perspectives. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 6(4), 343–357. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSMA-03-2013-0014>
- Barker, V. L., & Mueller, G. C. (2002). CEO characteristics and firm R&D spending. *Management Science*, 48(6), 782–801. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.48.6.782.187>
- Cai, W., Lysova, E. I., Khapova, S. N., & Bossink, B. A. G. (2018). Servant leadership and innovative work behavior in Chinese high-tech firms: A moderated mediation model of meaningful work and job autonomy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9(OCT). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01767>
- Cho, S. Y., & Kim, S. K. (2017). Horizon problem and firm innovation: The influence of CEO career horizon, exploitation and exploration on breakthrough innovations. *Research Policy*, 46(10), 1801–1809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2017.08.007>
- Galasso, A., & Simcoe, T. S. (2011). CEO overconfidence and innovation. *Management Science*, 57(8), 1469–1484. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1110.1374>
- Gottesman, A. A., & Morey, M. R. (2010). CEO Educational Background and Firm Financial Performance. In *Journal of applied finance* (Issue 2).
- Green, C. P., & Homroy, S. (2018). Female directors , board committees and firm performance. *European Economic Review*, 102, 19–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroecorev.2017.12.003>
- Hill, R. (1998). What sample size is enough pilot study. *An Electronic Journal for the 21st Century*, 6(3), 1–10.
- Isaac, S., & Michael, W. B. (1995). Handbook in research and evaluation: A collection of principles, methods, and strategies useful in the planning, design, and evaluation of studies in education and the behavioral sciences, 3rd ed. In *Handbook in research and evaluation: A collection of principles, methods, and strategies useful in the planning, design, and evaluation of studies in education and the behavioral sciences*, 3rd ed. EdITS Publishers.
- Jayaraman, N., Khorana, A., Nelling, E., & Covin, J. (2000). RESEARCH NOTES AND COMMENTARIES CEO FOUNDER STATUS AND FIRM FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE. In *Strategic Management Journal Strat. Mgmt. J* (Vol. 21).
- Johanson, G. A., & Brooks, G. P. (2010). Initial scale development: Sample size for pilot studies. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 70(3), 394–400. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164409355692>
- Khan, W. A., & Vieito, J. P. (2013). Ceo gender and firm performance. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 67, 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2013.01.003>
- King, T., Srivastav, A., & Williams, J. (2016). What’s in an education? Implications of CEO education for bank performance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 37, 287–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2016.01.003>
- Kitchell, S. (1997). CEO Characteristics and Technological Innovativeness: A Canadian Perspective. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 14(2), 111–121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1936-4490.1997.tb00123.x>

- Le Blanc, P. M., González-Romá, V., & Wang, H. (2021). Charismatic Leadership and Work Team Innovative Behavior: the Role of Team Task Interdependence and Team Potency. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 36(2), 333–346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-019-09663-6>
- Lee, J. M., Kim, J., & Bae, J. (2020). Founder CEOs and innovation: Evidence from CEO sudden deaths in public firms. *Research Policy*, 49(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103862>
- Li, M., & Yang, J. (2019). Effects of CEO duality and tenure on innovation. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 12(4), 536–552. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSMA-04-2019-0049>
- Liu, D., Fisher, G., & Chen, G. (2018). CEO attributes and firm performance: A sequential mediation process model. *Academy of Management Annals*, 12(2), 789–816. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2016.0031>
- Ministry of Information and Communication. (2023). ICT BUSINESS STATISTICS. Ministry of Information and Communication. <https://makeinvietnam.mic.gov.vn/ThongKeBaoCao/DoanhNghiep>
- Nguyen, P., Rahman, N., & Zhao, R. (2018). CEO characteristics and firm valuation: a quantile regression analysis. *Journal of Management and Governance*, 22(1), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10997-017-9383-7>
- Prasad, B., & Junni, P. (2017). A contingency model of CEO characteristics and firm innovativeness: The moderating role of organizational size. *Management Decision*, 55(1), 156–177. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-02-2016-0071>
- Rahman, M. J., & Chen, X. (2022). CEO characteristics and firm performance: evidence from private listed firms in China. *Corporate Governance (Bingley)*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-01-2022-0004>
- Salehi, M., & Moghadam, S. M. (2019). The relationship between management characteristics and firm performance. *Competitiveness Review*, 29(4), 440–461. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CR-11-2018-0070>
- Shen, W., & Cannella, A. A. (2002). REVISITING THE PERFORMANCE CONSEQUENCES OF CEO SUCCESSION: THE IMPACTS OF SUCCESSOR TYPE, POSTSUCCESSION SENIOR EXECUTIVE TURNOVER, AND DEPARTING CEO TENURE. In *Management Journal* (Vol. 45, Issue 4). Zajac.
- Wang, G., Holmes, R. M., Oh, I. S., & Zhu, W. (2016). Do CEOs Matter to Firm Strategic Actions and Firm Performance? A Meta-Analytic Investigation Based on Upper Echelons Theory. *Personnel Psychology*, 69(4), 775–862. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12140>
- Wang, Q., Pei, X., & Liang, H. (2022). Founder CEO, CEO Characteristics, and Firm Innovation Efficiency: An Empirical Study of China's GEM-Listed Companies. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148250>